

Blok realizujący proces formowania w alternatywnej postaci (bez używania Timerów wbudowanych sterownika PLC)

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"NewFormingProcessData".Pi :=
"ActiveRecipeData".PressingTimes["NewFormingProcessData".iterator];

"NewFormingProcessData".Ui :=
"ActiveRecipeData".UnpressingTimes["NewFormingProcessData".iterator];

"NewFormingProcessData".SlowPressing_i :=
"ActiveRecipeData".SlowPressing["NewFormingProcessData".iterator];

"NewFormingProcessData".SlowUnpressing_i :=
"ActiveRecipeData".SlowUnpressing["NewFormingProcessData".iterator];

IF "NewFormingProcessData".iterator < 19 THEN

  IF "ActiveRecipeData".PressingTimes["NewFormingProcessData".iterator + 1] = 0 THEN

    "NewFormingProcessData".LastProcess := TRUE;

  ELSE

    "NewFormingProcessData".LastProcess := FALSE;

  END_IF;

ELSIF "NewFormingProcessData".iterator = 19 THEN

  "NewFormingProcessData".LastProcess := TRUE;

END_IF;

CASE "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus OF

  "InitialDownMovement": // Statement section case 1

    IF ("SpeedDownSensor" = FALSE) THEN

      "FullSpeedMovement"();

    ELSE

      //TODO - przetestować poniższy kod z warunkiem

      IF "Main_DB".Clamp_pressure <
"NewFormingProcessData".MinimumOperatingPressure THEN

        "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "PressureTooLowError";

        "PressOutput" := FALSE;

        "Main_DB".FormingProcessON := FALSE;
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ELSE
    "PressOutput" := TRUE;
    "SteamVentilation" := TRUE;
    "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "PressingMove";
END_IF;
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END_IF;
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"PressingMove":
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"NewFormingProcessData".UnpressingDone := FALSE;
IF "NewFormingProcessData".SlowPressing_i > 0 THEN
    "SlowSpeedDown"();
ELSE
    "FullSpeedMovement"();
END_IF;
```

```
IF "NewFormingProcessData".UseOfDistanceSensorON = TRUE THEN
    IF "Main_DB".Distanceln_cm <= "NewFormingProcessData".MinimalDistance THEN
        "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "PressingHoldOn";
    END_IF;
ELSE
    IF "DownPositionSensor" = FALSE THEN
        "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "PressingHoldOn";
    END_IF;
END_IF;
```

```
"PressingHoldOn":
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IF "Main_DB".ClampForceValue >= "NewFormingProcessData".ClampForceUpperLimit
THEN
    "PressOutput" := FALSE;
END_IF;
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IF "NewFormingProcessData".Pi_Counter >= "NewFormingProcessData".Pi THEN
    "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "UnpressingMove";
    "PressOutput" := FALSE;
    "NewFormingProcessData".Ui_Counter := 0;
END_IF;

IF "NewFormingProcessData".FullSpeedOnPressingEnd = TRUE THEN
    "FullSpeedMovement"();
END_IF;

"UnpressingMove":
    IF "ActiveRecipeData".UnpressToHighSensor["NewFormingProcessData".iterator] > 0
    OR "NewFormingProcessData".UseOfDistanceSensorON THEN

        REGION Higher_Opening_Handling
            "OpeningControlFromDistanceSensor"();
        END_REGION

    ELSE

        IF "MiddlePositionActuatorSensor" = FALSE THEN
            "PressOutput" := FALSE;
            "UnpressOutput" := TRUE;
        END_IF;

        IF "NewFormingProcessData".FullSpeedOnReturning = FALSE THEN
            IF "NewFormingProcessData".SlowUnpressing_i > 0 THEN
                //IF "NewFormingProcessData".FastReturnCounter >= 100 THEN
                    "SlowSpeedUp"();
                //END_IF;
            ELSE
                "FullSpeedMovement"();
            END_IF;
        END_IF;
    END_IF;

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ELSE
    IF "NewFormingProcessData".FastReturnCounter >= TIME_TO_UINT(IN :=
"NewFormingProcessData".TimeForFullSpeedActivation) THEN
        "FullSpeedMovement"();
    ELSE
        IF "NewFormingProcessData".SlowUnpressing_i > 0 THEN
            "SlowSpeedUp"();
        ELSE
            "FullSpeedMovement"();
        END_IF;
    END_IF;
END_IF;

```

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IF "MiddlePositionActuatorSensor" = TRUE THEN
    "NewFormingProcessData".UnpressingDone := TRUE;
    IF "NewFormingProcessData".LastProcess = TRUE THEN
        "FullSpeedMovement"();
        "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "EndingMovementUp";
    ELSE
        "UnpressOutput" := FALSE;
        "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "UnpressingHold";
    END_IF;
END_IF;
END_IF;

```

"UnpressingHold":

```

IF "NewFormingProcessData".Ui_Counter >= "NewFormingProcessData".Ui THEN
    "NewFormingProcessData".Pi_Counter := 0;
    "NewFormingProcessData".FastReturnCounter := 0;

    IF "NewFormingProcessData".iterator < 19 THEN

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IF "NewFormingProcessData".UnpressingDone = TRUE THEN
    "NewFormingProcessData".iterator += 1;
    "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "PressingMove";
    "PressOutput" := TRUE;
END_IF;
ELSE
    "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "EndingMovementUp";
END_IF;
END_IF;

"EndingMovementUp":
    IF "PneumaticActuatorUpPosition" = TRUE THEN
        "Main_DB".FormingProcessON := FALSE;
        "SteamVentilation" := FALSE;
        "Main_DB".ProductReceived := FALSE;
        "Main_DB".DailyProduction += 1;
        "Main_DB".TotalProduction += 1;
        "Main_DB".TotalPowerConsumtion +=
(DWORD_TO_UINT("PowerConsumptionControlInput") -
"Main_DB".PowerConsumtionCycleToCycle);
        "Main_DB".PowerConsumtionCycleToCycle :=
DWORD_TO_UINT("PowerConsumptionControlInput");
        "NewFormingProcessData".ProcessStatus := "ReadyToReceiveProduct";
    ELSE
        "FullSpeedMovement"();
        "UnpressOutput" := TRUE;
    END_IF;
END_CASE;

```